

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF FORMING THE COGNITIVE COMPETENCE OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS BASED ON AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH

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Annotation: the article covers the development of knowledge of elementary school students based on an integrative approach, the formation of cognitive educational activity to increase the effectiveness of education, and the theoretical foundations of cognitive activity technology.

Key words: integrative approach, primary education, student, knowledge, development, cognitive educational activity, educational efficiency, technology of cognitive activity, theoretical basis.

Introduction:

The work carried out within the framework of the national curriculum in the field of primary education has led to a number of positive changes and is accelerating the increase in the quality and efficiency of education. Forming the mechanisms that form the motivations of students to learn and the formation of their cognitive and educational process system, in particular, the cognitive educational activities of elementary school students, through new forms of non-traditional methods of teaching requires the creation of theoretical foundations of technology. A new approach to the issues of providing education to students is the demand of the times. In the organization of lessons and extracurricular activities in primary classes, systematization, clear goal orientation, control of the results of teaching and introduction of new methods for evaluation are not reflected enough. Therefore, it is becoming an urgent issue to use active methods of education and upbringing, to find ways to rationally use acceptable forms of teaching and testing in general education schools in the improvement of educational methodological work. It is known that teaching methods consist of the teacher's activities with students in order to achieve certain goals, and serve to reveal the issues of who needs to be taught what and how. Therefore, the appropriate selection of forms and methods used to activate the cognitive activities of primary school students and their independent, creative thinking will be effective in the future training of personnel.

Today, along with the pedagogical goals of education, attention is paid to the development of learners and the formation of cognitive educational activities. The need to form the cognitive activity of primary school students is increasing. Cognitive functioning includes understanding how different students go through the process of thinking and understanding, how they receive, process and remember information, as well as the relatively stable individual characteristics of problem solving¹.

Everything in life consists of a moment of enlightenment. In the words of William Jordan: "Each servant is given an invisible power - through which a person influences his life.

¹ G.I. Shukin, Pedagogical problems of forming students' cognitive interests: textbook - M.: Pedagogika, 2008. - 296 p.

This force, which has a positive or negative effect, is a force that constantly radiates from the inner "I" of a person. But the reality is a little different. We do not see this world as it is. On the contrary, the way we are, the world is formed before our eyes. When we open our mouths to say what we see, we actually begin to describe ourselves, our perceptions, our paradigms.

Cognitive activity as a pedagogical phenomenon is a two-way interrelated process: on the one hand, cognitive activity is a form of student self-organization and self-awareness; on the other hand, cognitive activity is considered as the result of the teacher's special actions in organizing the student's cognitive activity.

Literature analysis and methodology

In a number of studies of Western scientists, the theoretical foundations of the study of cognitive activity have been considered. A theoretical basis is a review of previous work that indirectly supports the research under study. The technology of formation of cognitive educational activity of elementary school students is another important element of our new work, a new approach and additional information in relation to other studies. A theoretical framework can be developed by referring to various sources and using concepts and books that allow us to enrich our research work.

Research scientist L.V. Zankov emphasized that cognitive activity "*develops students' thinking and emotional sphere, teaches them to understand and determine the general meaning and main content of the material.*" I.F. Kharlamov interpreted cognitive activity as "an active state characterized by the student's desire to learn, mental effort and manifestation of voluntary actions in the process of acquiring knowledge"².

Active perception of the studied material and in understanding, it is of great importance that the teacher can give his presentation a charming character, make it lively and interesting. First of all, we should not forget that the educational material itself contains many stimuli that stimulate the interest and mental activity of students. These include the novelty of scientific information, the brightness of facts, the uniqueness of conclusions, a unique approach to the consideration of established ideas, and deep penetration into the essence of events.

G.I. Shchukina considered cognitive activity "representing the unique state of the student and his attitude to activity", "valuable and complex personal education of the student, which is intensively formed during the school years"³.

A.K. Markova understood this educational activity as "knowing all types of active attitude to education: the existence of meaning, the importance of learning as knowledge for a child, all types of cognitive motives." The types of cognitive motives include: broad cognitive (orientation to acquire new knowledge - facts, events, laws), educational and cognitive motives (to master the methods of acquiring knowledge, methods of self-acquisition of knowledge or 'naughty').

M.D. Vinogradov and I.B. Pervin believed that collective cognitive activity plays an important role in the development of cognitive activity. Its various forms stimulate creativity, fantasy, imagination, cognitive activity and independence. Students should be taught to work

² S.R. Kovi, "Seven skills of successful people" (translated from English by Orifakhon Gulomova), "Nihol" publishing house-2020, p. 16.

³ Щукина Г.И. Усиление когнитивной активности в процессе образования. –М., Образование, 2005 год.

in a team. It is equally important to create an atmosphere of mutual respect, goodwill, attention to each other and sensitivity in the classroom, so that each student has a positive attitude towards learning and actively participates in it.

E. N. Kabanova considers the system of forming generalized methods of educational work, which are important components of effective educational activity of students in the development of cognitive activity. In his opinion, the methods of cognitive activity are methods of mental work that ensure the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities, their independent application and active change, the use of a system of tools for activating cognitive activity, understanding the purpose of activity at the stage of forming a cognitive motive, helps to form creative use, productive independent work skills, generalized learning skills.

Z.I. Kalmykova believed that problem-based education is the leading condition for the development of cognitive activity. The problem principle is aimed at discovering new knowledge and is the leading principle of developmental education.

In the 1970s and 1980s, I.S. Yakimanskaya made extensive contributions to cognitive activity. According to him, not all education really has a developmental effect, although it does not exclude the cognitive activity of students. Cognitive activity is the most important source of mental development only when it turns into self-activity. Forming this self-activity is the most important task of developmental education.

Cognitive activity is defined by T.I. Shamova: "Activity in educational activity... is not only the student's state of activity, but also... it is the quality of the activity, in which the personality of the student is manifested in relation to the content, nature and activity of the activity. , interpreted as the desire to mobilize one's spiritual and volitional efforts to achieve an educational and cognitive goal. This definition seems to be the most complete, because it reflects not only the psychological aspects of cognitive activity, the state of activity, the quality of this activity, but also the social aspects of the personality of students and their attitude to its content and content. It also names the tools that activate cognitive activity: activity, interest, development of the motivational field, volitional qualities (a person's desire to mobilize spiritual and volitional efforts) and the specific destination of applying these actions (for educational and cognitive purposes reach).

T.I. Shamova does not reduce cognitive activity to mental and simple tension, but considers it as a personal activity that manifests itself in the student's attitude to the content and process of activity, in the effort to effectively acquire knowledge and activity methods at the optimal time, and in the mobilization of moral and willpower.

Results and discussion

In the process of forming the need for educational activities among primary school students, it is concretized in various motives, which requires children to behave. Cognitive activity is based on changing the educational material, introducing the student to the origin of knowledge by highlighting the most fundamental, basic concepts. Pedagogical reality proves every day that the educational process will be more effective if the student is cognitively active. This phenomenon is strengthened in the theory of pedagogy as the principle of "*activity and independence of students in learning*".

It is important for teachers who organize the learning process to know the structure of the activity. Its main components are: motives, purpose, tasks, content, means, forms, methods and result. So, the teacher should influence the emotional-motivational, mental, and practical spheres of the students' personality with the help of various means. It is also

important for teachers to know the main types of activities in which schoolchildren participate: academic-cognitive, social, work, play, aesthetic, sports and recreation. Interlinking these activities is very important. The primary school teacher is largely the organizer of students' cognitive independent activities. Cognitive education is currently achieved through alternative programs, differentiated methods, creative homework, extracurricular forms of student activity organization. Modern studies of psychologists on cognitive education convincingly prove that the cognitive activity of students when solving research problems differs from solving standardized problems.

Cognitive activity reflects the constant need of young students to use new knowledge, skills, internal purposefulness and various methods of action to supplement knowledge, expand knowledge and expand their horizons⁴.

The problem of the formation of cognitive activity at the personal level, as evidenced by the analysis of literary sources, is related to the consideration of the motivation of cognitive activity and methods of formation of cognitive interests. Cognitive activity can be considered as a manifestation of all aspects of the student's personality: it is interest in new things, the desire for success, the joy of learning, as well as the attitude to solving problems, its gradual complexity.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, it can be said that cognitive activity is an important activity that determines the student's own position, willingness to learn and desire to gain a new position in society. Elementary school students joyful anticipation of the school day passes among first grade students, the initial enthusiasm for learning appears. Therefore, it is necessary to awaken such motives, which lie in the learning process, and not outside.

In educational activities, the child works with scientific concepts under the guidance of the teacher, learns them. As a result, changes occur in the student himself, in his development. Formation of cognitive educational activity of elementary school students, development of interests, education of active attitude to work, first of all, takes place in class. The student works with interest in the lesson. To do this, at each stage of any lesson, it is necessary to activate students' cognitive activity and increase interest in learning, use different methods, forms and types of work.

⁴ Levels of cognitive activity: textbook / T.I. Shamov. - M.: Education, 2005. - 286 p.

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